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**DEVELOPMENT OF “KALASAG”: A MODERN SECURITY JACKET FOR
PERSONS WITH DISABILITY**

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DEVELOPMENT OF “KALASAG”: A MODERN SECURITY JACKET FOR PERSONS WITH DISABILITY

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Hannah De Lara Beraquit September 24, 2024

Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **HANNAH D. BERAQUIT** with the title: “ **Development of “Kalasag”**: A modern security jacket for Persons with Disability ” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

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Apart from her career, she likes to delve into Music production and Dressmaking. When she was 9, she first learned about her love for music after learning Piano. Today, she uses this skill in creating original compositions—drawing inspiration from the music of Porter Robinson, Keshi, and Jon Bellion. By the age of 16, she acquired her love for fashion and was able to acquire her NC II certificate in Dressmaking and continues to use her attainment in academic and professional goals, drawing inspiration from Viktor & Rolf, Schiaparelli, and Guo Pei.

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ABSTRACT

The increasing need for enhanced safety and security for persons with disabilities (PWDs) has prompted the development of specialized assistive technologies, also categorized as wearable technologies. This thesis presents the design, development, and evaluation of "Kalasag", which is a modern security jacket for PWDs, specifically for the Deaf, who currently face language barriers amidst verbal and non-verbal communication.

The jacket integrates a range of features, including a help caller, security alarm system, and digital health record, embedded in a multifunctional jacket to address various safety challenges faced by individuals with sensory impairments.

Employing a user-centered design approach, the project involved consultation with PWDs and experts in clothing and assistive technology to ensure that the jacket meets practical needs while maintaining comfort and ease of use.

The development process of the prototype utilized materials and technologies that enhance durability, functionality, and user comfort, including non-static fabrics and the use of basic electronics. Evaluation results from the creative project involving a target group of three Deaf participants demonstrate that Kalasag has shown potential to improve users' confidence in their personal safety and facilitate efficient emergency response.

This thesis concludes with recommendations toward the incorporation of more advanced technology and in-depth research towards the creation of the jacket for other PWD classifications for further refinement of the jacket's features and potential pathways for commercial production and broader dissemination. The findings contribute to the ongoing efforts to enhance the quality of life for PWDs through innovative assistive solutions.

Keywords: Wearables, PWD, Deaf, Security, Jacket, Technology

I. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The Philippines continues to be surrounded by dangers caused by crime, natural calamities, and other unexpected occurrences (Mantaring, 2023). Amidst these risks in society, each individual must have the capability to protect themselves from harm, even those with certain capabilities.

Conversely to the safety of the members of society, Harell (2021) states that victims of nonfatal crimes compose 26% of the population of persons with disabilities. Additionally, 33% of persons with disabilities are victims of robbery or thievery. The same study also show that 19% of Persons with Disabilities (PWD) are reported to have experienced rape or abuse.

For this reason, there is a need for the PWD to have a sense of security measure that they can utilize during emergencies. This document details the development of “Kalasag”, an experimental/advocacy safety project dedicated to creating a modern wearable jacket to support persons with disabilities to act during emergencies such as thievery, physical abuse, and sexual harassment. The goal of this project is to combine fashion and technology while maintaining the highest level of functionality. This project aims to contribute to the development of a safe environment for people with disabilities, the inclusion of PWD welfare in our country, and the revolutionization of fashion and technology in the Philippines. The definition of Kalasag, according to Kalasag : Binisaya Cebuano to English Dictionary, originates from the Filipino language, which means ‘shield’. In the Bisaya language, it may refer to protective clothing

that is embedded with their tribe's insignia. (Kalasag : Binisaya - Cebuano to English Dictionary and Thesaurus., 2007).

The wearable device endeavors to safeguard the user or an individual with disabilities from unforeseen circumstances, particularly criminal incidents, by its given nomenclature. Regarding the advent of emerging wearables and their potential advantages for humanity, it is appropriate to examine the underlying catalyst for this innovation: contemporary technology.

Conversely, the article by Scientific Research and Experimental Development (2022) highlights that modern technology advancement, an era characterized by the discovery and exploration of science, has played a crucial role in enabling groundbreaking innovations like wearables. This era has opened doors for individuals to reimagine and devise new solutions to address existing problems, including those about safety and protection, even within the realm of clothing.

Particularly, one of these technological advancements is the emerging wearable technologies. Hayes' journal (2022) *What Is Wearable Technology (Wearables)?* defined wearable technologies as electronic devices that can be worn by individuals in the form of clothing and accessories. He emphasized that these are usually hands-free devices that make use of processors and the internet to carry out different empirical tasks.

Furthermore, Chopra & Singhal's (2021) journal article defined wearable technology as intelligent devices that can be worn near or over the skin and recognize, explore, and send relevant data, such as body gestures or signals, imperative signs, or surrounding information, and in some cases provide immediate bio-feedback to the wearer.

Additionally, Piad's (2022) article explained that the growth of wearable technology in the Philippines has slowly increased by 23.7% percent with Filipinos getting accustomed to fitness trackers such as wristbands and smartwatches. The International Data Corporation's report (IDC) (as cited by Piad, 2022), states that the shipment of wearables in the Philippines increased dramatically in 2022. During the third quarter of the year, approximately 370,000 wearables were imported. Local companies such as Cherry Mobile have released their own version of a smartwatch through their MediaTek-powered smartwatches, the G series, N series, and Flare watch series. Wearable company owner Angelo Umali has also explored the use of wearables in the medical field where the company developed a watch that detects fainting. The said wearable is now being used and pilot tested by The Medical City. The presented data indicate that smartwatches hold a significant position among wearable devices in the Philippines.

The following section discusses the jacket's epistemology and its significance to this endeavor. This initiative will focus specifically on the development of a jacket for the disabled. The Merriam-Webster Dictionary (n.d) defined a jacket as a garment that is worn on the upper part of the body.

Originating from the Middle French noun *jaquet*, a jacket refers to a light garment worn from the shoulders towards the waist (Military Republic, 2018).

Following further the history of the jacket, one of its earlier forms was its emergence in the 17th century, known as the Mackintosh Jacket. The Mackintosh Jacket was first invented by Scottish Inventor Charles Macintosh in 1824. This type of garment was made from waterproof fabric and was commonly known as the Macintosh coat during its time. This garment refers to a simple, utilitarian jacket that was meant to keep the wearer safe from the rain. Its original design refers to a jacket dropping from the shoulders to the hips with long sleeves that fell to the wrist. It was known to have a belt that tied the whole jacket by the waist. Its unique feature was the absence of a seam by the shoulder blades to avoid water from seeping through the jacket.

In today's modern world, jackets have been designed to serve their use for different events as protective wear. Harper (2016) states in their online article that jackets have been developed to serve specific purposes rather than protecting oneself from the cold such as bulletproof jackets, insulated jackets, and military jackets. Jackets' sole purpose in society has now become a necessity, not only used to protect the wearer from the weather but also for everyday use (Parks, 2023). This has been the basis of why the project focused on creating a jacket to protect the PWD from dangers and ensure their independence as members of society.

The United Nations of Human Rights (2006) report defined Persons with Disabilities (PWD) as individuals who experience long-term ailments. These include conditions that are related to physical, mental, intellectual, or sensory properties that hinder a person from completing their responsibilities as members of society.

As a matter of fact, a statistical report conducted by the World Health Organization (2023) explained that 16% of the population, or 1.6 billion people, have a form of disability. This means that almost 1 in 6 individuals are unable to carry out specific activities due to their condition.

Moreover, the same report from the World Health Organization (WHO) cites the severity of disability worldwide from the World Health Survey. According to the report, 110 million people (2.2%) have significant disabilities that pose difficulty in functioning such as mental and physical ailments, On the contrary, WHO also cites the Global Burden of Disease, stating that an approximation of 190 million (3.8%) have “severe disability” or individuals suffering disabilities equal to quadriplegia, severe depression, or blindness.

According to the Department of Health's official website, as of 2023, the current data shows that among the 92.1 million population of the Philippines, approximately 1.57% are categorized as Persons with Disabilities (PWD). This corresponds to a significant number of nearly 1.9 million individuals in the country.

Additionally, the executive department states that Region IV-A is leading with the number of PWD in the country and the Cordillera Administrative Region with the lowest, accounting for up to 260,000 individuals. Data also shows that out of five PWD, three individuals are ages 16 to 64.

With the prominent number of PWD here in the Philippines, the local government aims to provide equal opportunities and rights for these individuals through the law.

According to The Magna Carta for Disabled Persons series of 1992, or Republic Act No. 7277, the state aims to assist individuals with disabilities in achieving a fulfilling and productive life within society. The state is committed to providing equal employment opportunities, financial assistance, healthcare services, rehabilitation centers, and auxiliary social services to individuals with disabilities. The goal is to enable individuals with disabilities to lead meaningful and satisfying lives.

In addition, Republic Act No 7277 also prioritizes the welfare of disabled individuals. Other than the mandatory allotment for PWD-supported structures in public places, the law ensures the accessibility of health care nationwide. As stated in Chapters III to IV of RA 7277, the state shall ensure that the Department of Health must allot a certain budget to the creation of rehabilitation centers and hospitals for the disabled. Affordable health care is also prioritized by the state. Services such as the prevention of disability through immunization, nutrition, environmental protection and preservation,

genetic counseling; and early detection of disability and timely intervention to arrest disabling conditions. Doctors and medical personnel are also required to undergo training for medical attention targeted to the disabled. This law aims to reach equity among members of society, even the disabled. It ensures that persons with disabilities are protected by the law wherein the state removes all barriers that may hinder the PWD to be members of society.

Moreover, the Republic Act No 7277 also warns the public against discrimination in employment, public services, and transportation. Individuals who shall violate the law or act upon discrimination of the PWD will be punished by the law where offenders will pay a fine of 50,000 to 100,000 PHP for the first offense and 100,000 to 200,000 PHP or two to six years imprisonment for the second offense. Contrary to the penalty against discrimination, this law has yet to protect the security of the PWD against occurring crimes. This is what makes Kalasag a crucial project for the safety of the PWD.

To better comprehend the purpose of the wearable, it is necessary to discuss the concept of societal security. For the context of this creative project, the Britannica Dictionary (n.d) defines security as the state of being protected from unwanted forces or the state of being safe. According to the Human and Peoples' Rights Declaration of the Philippines Article III, as cited by Amnesty International (2013), each individual has the right to security. Although a right, security in the country continues to be threatened by dangers, specifically from crimes.

According to a statistical report by the Statista Research Department for the year 2022, the Philippines have a moderately high rate of crime, violence, and terrorism. With an order and security index of only 0.62 in 2021, the nation will also be one of the top countries with the highest crime rate.

Additionally, the Directorate for Investigation and Detective Management (2022) has also plotted a total of 85,701 crime incidents in the Philippines from January to March of 2022. Alarmingly, theft and rape are the leading crime cases with 2,786 and 1,588 incidents, respectively, during that period. This state of the Philippines makes it more difficult for PWD to defend themselves due to incapacibilities that make it difficult for them to defend themselves (Luna, 2020).

An online article by Hood (2022) explains that approximately half of young women who are deaf have experienced sexual abuse; this is almost twice the rate of girls without hearing impairment. Furthermore, more than half of young males who are deaf have been sexually abused, which is five times more than boys who are hearing. Around 80% of females and 30% of males who have developmental disabilities have also been subjected to sexual assault. Among these women, half of them have experienced more than ten assaults. These instances of crimes against PWD are not only limited to other countries but also the Philippines.

Moreover, crime rates tend to be more targeted among PWD individuals. The US Department of Justice notes that 36 per 1,000 individuals with disabilities are victims of crime in comparison to the 14 per 1000 rate for those without disabilities (Harell, 2015).

Locally, the Philippine Statistics Authority has reported that 1.4% of persons with disabilities aged 15 years and over experienced physical abuse during the year 2016 in their statistical report .

For instance, Luna (2020) in his article reported that a 10-year-old PWD girl was murdered by a 52-year-old pedophile in the Philippines. This report revealed that the actual perception of PWDs in the Philippines is 'helpless,' and marginalized people are more likely to become victims of crime. This data or precedent cases show the vulnerability of PWD in the country and the lack of national security towards PWD.

In brief, data shown by numerous sources just proves the need for Kalasag for the protection of the PWD against unprecedented crimes in the Philippines to ensure their independence as individuals in their society.

Being said, the creative project aims to facilitate the creation of a secure environment for persons with disabilities through the utilization of jackets, which can aid in the enforcement of laws in the Philippines that promote the security and well-being of this population.

Google Scholar shows that there are almost 14,700 international studies regarding wearables for persons with disabilities. Top studies of the search have a direct relation with health care to monitor disabilities such as Alzheimer's syndrome, dementia, and such.

According to the same search engine, there are also 804 studies about wearables in the Philippines. However, these studies primarily focus on healthcare relating to fitness and lifestyle, including using medical instruments.

At present, a lack of localized inquiry into the safeguarding of persons with disabilities via wearable technologies is evident in the Philippines, as per the Philippine E-Journal website, there are 145 journals related to the PWD but none about security wearables. The UPOU repository appears to exhibit a dearth of research on wearables, with only one study by Maranan et al. (2019) being documented. This observation suggests the existence of a research gap in this area. Studies showed the lack of resources on security wearables in the Philippines may also be due to wearable technology, a new technology trend that is yet to be explored in the country (Castillo, 2022).

This creative project can contribute to the development of future wearable technologies that aims to improve the safety and well-being of individuals with disabilities. The necessity of conducting this project in the Philippines lies in its potential to contribute to the progress and enhancement of policies and legislation concerning Persons with Disabilities (PWD) in the forthcoming times.

Definition of Terms

1. Persons with Disabilities - refer to individuals with long-term impairments, whether physical, mental, or emotional, that do not allow them to fully function in society.
2. Wearables - these are electronic devices that can be worn on the body to complete empirical tasks through sensors and computing capabilities.
3. Security - the state of being protected from dangers in society.
4. Technology - refers to anything that is powered through electrical means that is used to perform tasks.
5. Deaf - refers to a specific community of individuals who are hard of hearing. In this capstone project, this refers to the target group that has speech impairment.
6. Electronics - these are components that make use of a power supply to perform certain tasks.
7. Prototype - refers to an early model of a device that is not made to be distributed to the market.
8. FSL - also known as Filipino Sign Language. It is a non-verbal language used by the Deaf, specifically used in the Philippines.
9. Kalasag - refers to the name of the output of this project which aims to create a modern security jacket for Persons with Disability.
10. Help Center - refers to locations where individuals can ask assistance in case of emergencies such as Police Stations, Hospitals, etc

Statement of the Problem

The capstone project aimed to develop a novel wearable technology project entitled "Kalasag" that is designed to enhance the safety and well-being of Persons with Disability. The project involved the construction of a modern security jacket that incorporates innovative features to support the aforementioned objectives. This project aimed to document the design process of a highly advanced wearable jacket that is specifically intended to aid Persons With Disabilities (PWD) in the Philippines during emergency scenarios such as thievery, robbery, sexual harassment, and physical abuse.

The purpose of this project is to develop a wearable jacket that will serve as a security measure against critical crimes and calamities that will allow the independence of Persons with Disabilities while outdoors. This creative project further seeks to address the following questions:

1. What is the design process of "Kalasag": A modern security jacket for Persons with Disability aged 16 to 20 years old?
2. How does Kalasag ensure their safety during emergency scenarios?

Significance of the Study

The findings of this creative project may contribute to multimedia studies as a discipline and in its growing area of research by developing creative research on the design process "Kalasag": A modern security jacket for Persons with Disability aged 16 to 20 years old. This would also benefit the following stakeholders:

This creative project can serve as a reference for future researchers on PWD, wearable technologies, and clothing technology research on the practical aspects of fashion in the Philippines. The findings of this creative project can be used as a guide for future innovative wearable production and research projects aimed at ensuring the safety and well-being of PWDs.

Furthermore, PWDs will benefit from this project because they will have clothing that will help them feel safe because of its security features. To ensure the safety of Filipinos with disabilities, the development of this project will provide an impetus for new research on the creation of comfortable and wearable devices.

With the crime rates of theft and rate being most prominent in the Philippines, the project will mainly focus on creating a wearable jacket that will protect individuals from these specific scenarios during their commute.

In addition, curriculum developers and professors may consider this creative project as a potential project for their students. This project can serve as a resource for future student exploratory projects involving wearables in the Philippines.

This creative project will also serve as a guide for plans to replicate or enhance the product currently under development. Students will comprehend how technology can be incorporated into wearables and the design process.

Students can gain a deeper understanding of how to design user-centric wearable technology for marginalized groups by utilizing this resource.

This creative project can be used by policymakers, government offices, and LGUs as a basis for the development of future equipment and technology that will enable PWD individuals to practice independence even in the absence of a companion. This research can also be used as a resource for developing policies or programs to ensure the safety of individuals with disabilities.

Lastly, this creative project will serve as a reference for improving safety protocols for PWDs in the country.

Scope and Limitations

The scope of this project is the developmental process of designing Kalasag: A modern security jacket for persons with disabilities. This project focused on a security jacket against common crimes experienced in the Philippines. Specifically, this creative project focused on self-defense against robbery and sexual harassment.

This creative project describes the design process behind creating Kalasag using the concept of The Interaction Design Process Foundation's (2022) design thinking process for human-centered design. The following steps are an iteration of the process:

1. Research: This step focused on finding existing data about the target group i.e. persons with disabilities.
2. Synthesize: Data collected from the user group was be synthesized to conclude the problems that need to be addressed.
3. Designing: A rough idea of the project was be created during this phase. It identified key features of the product and its functionalities through sketching.
4. Prototyping: This included the creation of the product itself through using prototype means and such.
5. Testing: The developed prototype was then be tested with the help of key informants.

This creative project focueds on creating a prototype where there was no experimentation in a control group and data gathering was be limited to key informants and three Deaf individuals. Furthermore, this is an exploratory creative project with a limited budget. This jacket remains as a prototype and involve basic electronic components available to the scope of a student.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter discusses related studies and existing data on the said project: (1) Modern Technology (2) Electronics in the Philippines (3) Development of Wearables (4) Development of Wearables (5) Persons with Disabilities (6) Security (7) Design Thinking Process (8) Conceptual Framework. In this review of related literature, I aim to recognize the current landscape of wearables in the Philippines and its possible potential to enforce security and promote independence for persons with disabilities (PWD).

Modern Technology

Wearable technology has truly made a huge breakthrough during the digital era, transforming human's daily lives through efficiency and convenience. This is seen to be true as stated by the International Trade Administration (2024) as the Philippine digital economy grew to \$36.5 billion, making up 9.4% of the GDP, up 11% from 2021, making modern technology, such as Digital-enabling infrastructures, the largest contributor in the local economy.

According to Spacey's (2022) study, they define Modern technology as any product that has been created through the use of science. This often involves the application of engineering and information technology such as the use of software, computers, and networks. Some examples of modern technology include the use of advanced materials such as databases, cloud computing, and the internet. Similarly, Swalih's (2023) study defined Modern Technology as an evolution from old technology. They emphasize the impact of

modern technology wherein its purpose can take the form of efficiency while maintaining accuracy. Such products have been a major breakthrough in different disciplines such as education, business, medicine, agriculture, etc. Along with these disciplines, is the major contribution of electronics to the breakthrough of technology in the country.

Electronics in the Philippines

According to Awan et al (2017), the electronics manufacturing sector is an essential part of the Philippines' industries that continues to hold great value in the economy. In 2016, the Philippines recorded electronics exports worth \$28.6 billion, which encompasses over 50% of its total exports. This industry has not only aided in providing employment opportunities, but has also attracted foreign direct investment from multinational corporations such as Intel, Acer, Texas Instruments, and Toshiba.

Additionally, Giray (2020) predicts that a total of \$8.1 billion worth of spending on consumer electronics is expected between 2020 and 2024, with roughly \$6 billion expected in 2020 alone. Some of the top categories that boost this spending include buying of mobile phones, computer hardware, and audiovisual equipment. A new middle class is also developing, with 1.5 million households expected to make \$25,000 or more by 2024. This generation is keen to own mobile devices, televisions, and potentially PCs, which has potentially led to the ever growing world that led to the Digital Era.

Digital Era

According to a journal by Doukidis (n.d), the Digital Era is characterized by technological advancements that enforce speed and convenience of information exchange in society. It can be perceived as an evolutionary system where knowledge turnover is not only high but also increasingly beyond human control, making it challenging to manage our lives.

The Global Digital 2019 Report by Kemp (2019) shows the growth of the digital era as the number of users in which there are 5.112 billion mobile users, 4.388 billion internet users and 3.484 billion active social media users in the year 2019.

According to the United Nations (n.d), this digital transformation has reached almost 50% of the population, making a substantial impact on access to the trade and education industry. Arising new technology, such as artificial intelligence (AI) and data pooling can be applied in different fields such as agriculture, health, and the environment, to innovate solutions that can be applied in solving day-to-day concerns. One of these arising technologies that aim to create an impact in society would be the production of wearables, which are accessible devices worn on the body that serve various purposes to aid human life.

Development of Wearables

Yasar (2023) defines wearable technology as a device such as jewelry, accessories, and other clothing that allows a user to carry out specific tasks, including executing processes that involve computing and communication.

These are usually devices that are composed of microprocessors, batteries, and connectivity to the internet that may or may not respond to bodily movements.

Belokopytov's (2022) website article entitled "Wearable Devices: Conditional Classification" discussed the criteria that is used to classify a wearable in the following: (1) device that is worn in close contact to the body, implanted to the body, taken orally, or attached to the human body (2) (3) The device must have an input/output mechanism wherein it is able to receive physiological information from the wearer and ,in turn, respond to human action (4) Information from the wearable corresponds to a certain central processor or towards a cloud storage (5) Device must allow **Biofeedback** (6) Wearable devices should have a sustainable and functional lifespan which should be used by consumers more permanently than other garments.

Singh Kang & Exworthy (2022) published a study on the potential of wearables where they state that it poses an important part of health and care. Wearables remain substantial as they can aid in numerous sectors towards accurate diagnosis, behavior change, and self-monitoring.

In the context of the Philippines, the presence of wearables has indeed evolved throughout the years and have also been used in varying disciplines. According to an article by Ubranis (2023), the growth of wearables can be seen in IDC's Worldwide Quarterly Wearable Device Tracker, wherein 370,000

units of wearable devices have been shipped during the third quarter of the year 2022.

In addition, the report also states that earwears were among the top devices used in the country, with 46.8 percent of wearable consumers purchasing these. This was then followed by fitness trackers in the form of wristbands, with a 46.5-percent growth from the previous year's 68,700 units.

According to a study conducted by Awan et al (2017), the electronics manufacturing or is an essential part of the Philippines' industries that continues to hold great value in the economy. In 2016, the Philippines recorded electronics exports worth \$28.6 billion, which encompasses over 50% of its total exports. This industry has not only aided in providing employment opportunities, but has also attracted foreign direct investment from multinational corporations such as Intel, Acer, Texas Instruments, and Toshiba. This data shows that the growth of the electronics sector will only continue to grow and continue to leave an impact on the economy, as plotted in the Philippine Development Plan Technology Economic Boost of Pagtanaw 2050, a foresight of the impact of technology in the Philippines created by the National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA) in 2023 .

Correspondingly, Castillo (2022) believes that bio wearables, or wearables play a significant role in the future of healthcare as it provides real-time data to help patients, doctors, and caregivers address health conditions promptly. These devices offer easy accessibility, allowing patients to

monitor their health data without the need for frequent clinic visits. Doctors can use this data to tailor personalized prescriptions for patients, while caregivers can provide data-driven care. Biowearables also assist patients in their recovery journey by showing the results of lifestyle changes and motivating them to improve their long-term health. Moreover, during events like a pandemic, cloud-enabled bio wearables enable remote data transmission, reducing the need for clinic visits and minimizing exposure risks for individuals with diabetes.

Persons with Disabilities

According to the National Council of Persons with Disabilities in connection to RA 10524, a person with disability can be defined as a person who is unable to fully participate as a member of their society due to existing long term physical, mental, intellectual, or sensory conditions on an equal plane as other of its members.

According to RA 7277, the Department of Health (DOH) recognizes seven types of disabilities. Psychosocial disability includes learned actions, cognitive abilities, emotional states, or social disabilities that hinder an individual from performing essential activities. Disability due to chronic illness refers to long-term medical conditions that can significantly impact human health or lead to death. Learning disabilities prevent individuals from engaging in activities like listening, thinking, reading, writing, spelling, and arithmetic, despite having all sensory functions. Mental disabilities arise from organic brain syndrome, such as mental retardation and acquired central nervous

system lesions. Visual disabilities result from the inability to see visual images clearly due to a long-term eye condition. Orthopedic disabilities relate to abnormal joint, muscle, and limb function due to natural or consequent occurrences. Speech and language disabilities involve one or more disorders affecting speech and language, including voice, articulation, and rhythm, as well as the receptive and expressive processes of language.

Under the law, the protection of PWD rights and privileges in the country lies in the Magna Carta for Disabled Persons, which was introduced by Senator Francisco “Kiko” Pangilinan. It provides general aid to those with disabilities and ensures equal rights in society. The law discusses seven sections towards inclusive employment, health, education, auxiliary social services, telecommunications, accessibility, and political rights.

Specifically, the penalty to discrimination against the PWD by Republic Act No. 7277 will be subject to legal sanctions, which include fines ranging from 50,000 to 100,000 PHP for a first offense and 100,000 to 200,000 PHP or two to six years in prison for a second.

The law also continues to support the lifestyle and leisure of the PWD by providing benefits such as discounts to specific goods and services. It also ensures that health centers are accessible and affordable to individuals of the community who need it.

The law was mainly created to protect the PWD from discrimination in the stated sectors of society. It penalizes individuals who deny the PWD rights to take part in numerous activities of its members of society. It allows individuals, even with disabilities, to take part in societal activities without barriers in society.

In addition to the Magna Carta for disabled persons, the Batas Pambansa Blg. 344 (Accessibility Law) as part of the country's legislation, was also established to ensure that the PWD are able to access public places.

According to the said law, no contract for construction, renovation, or expansion of buildings will be approved unless the building allocates plans towards building PWD accessible places. All infrastructure must adhere to the accessibility standards for the creation of ramps, railings, elevators, signage, parking spaces, and other features that make spaces accessible to PWDs

The enforcement of these accessibility standards is enforced by government agencies, primarily the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH). These agencies are responsible for overseeing adherence to the outlined accessibility guidelines. They possess the power to conduct building inspections, grant permits, and levy penalties in cases of non-compliance.

Furthermore, the Republic Act 6759 (White Cane Act) established in 1989 states the government's responsibility in promoting the welfare of blind individuals and all other handicapped individuals. It states the active

participation of government institutions in protecting these individuals. The law also upholds the importance of White Cane Safety Day for individuals in the country annually during the 1st of August to recognize the needed assistance of the blind in the country and to raise awareness on the population of the handicapped in the country.

On the contrary, despite the PWD's protection and benefits under the law, it is important to also highlight the right of security of our handicapped individuals.

Security

According to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), Article 3 states that 'everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person,'. This states that every individual should have the right to live freely and without the fear of danger such as crime, murder, or genocide (United Nations, n.d).

According to the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disability, Article 14 - 15, Persons with Disabilities have the right to equal security as everyone, regardless of disability. Any violation against their right, such as experiments, torture, and other inhuman treatments goes against this rights (Centre on Human Rights for People with Disabilities,nd) . Despite such rights, numerous PWD individuals remain victimized, especially in the country.

26% of people with disabilities are victims of nonfatal crimes, according to Harell (2021). Furthermore, 33% of people with disabilities are the victims of

theft or robbery. Additionally, according to statistics, 19% of people with disabilities (PWD) have been the victims of rape or other forms of violence.

The US Department of Justice notes that 36 per 1,000 individuals with disabilities are victims of crime in comparison to the 14 per 1000 rate for those without disabilities (Harell, 2015).

Locally, In its statistical report for 2016, the Philippine Statistics Authority stated that 1.4% of disabled people aged 15 and older had been physically abused. A total of 85,701 crimes in the Philippines from January to March 2022 have also been plotted by the Directorate for Investigation and Detective Management (2022). Alarmingly, with 2,786 and 1,588 incidences, respectively, at that time, theft and rape were the most common crimes.

Design Thinking Process

Interaction Design Process Foundation Design thinking process

The Design thinking process is defined as a non-linear, iterative approach, to comprehend users, question presumptions, reframe challenges, and develop original ideas for prototyping and testing. This method entails five steps (Empathize, Define, Ideate, Prototype, and Test), and is particularly beneficial when used in situations that lack available information on the field or needs primary data.

IDEO (2012) also highlights the essence of human centered design which is an iterative approach. They believe designs and prototypes are meant

to be revised throughout the process. It emphasizes the human element in designing that continues to improve based on feedback and calibration to create a viable and effective design towards solving real life solutions.

Additionally, IDEO also states the importance of execution and action. In contrast to centering around analysis and research, this type of approach encourages user testing by executing ideas. They make use of prototype testing to be one of the crucial parts of designing.

Synthesis

Modern technology continues to shape the behaviors of individuals and create solutions to efficiency and convenience (Swalih, 2023). This convenience has allowed technology to be one of the main reasons why the technology industry in the Philippines continues to show sudden growth in the year 2022. Giray (2020) also believes that \$8.1 billion worth of electronics is expected in the year 2020 and 2024.

Amidst the revolution of technology, one of the greatest breakthroughs of the digital era remains to be the creation of wearables in the Philippines. Yasar (n.d) defines this as items who make use of With the growth of wearables boosting up to 44% in comparison to the year 2022, we continue to see the economical impact of the technological industry in the Philippines.

Today, wearables are now seen as a technological advancement that take essential roles in healthcare, fitness, and mobile assist. Castillo (2022)

believes that the real-time data that wearables provide will greatly contribute in the medical field.

According to the Department of Health (n.d), Persons with disabilities refer to individuals who are experiencing long term conditions that do not allow a person to participate fully as a member of society.

Amidst discrimination and crimes against the PWD, the Philippine constitution has established laws that continue to protect the PWD and provide as stated in Republic Act No 7277 (Magna Carta for Disabled Persons), Republic Act 6759 (White Cane Act), and Batas Pambansa Blg. 344 (Accessibility Law).

While this is so, the rights of the Filipinos to remain secured continue to be violated due to crimes committed against persons with disabilities (Luna, 2020).

In 2016, the Philippine Statistic Authority has plotted the threat against the Persons with disabilities due to their hopelessness against crime. With the Philippines being rated as a country, it is only proper that the PWD should have the means to protect themselves against crimes. Reports on the recent 1.4% of persons with disabilities aged 15 years and over experienced physical abuse during the year 2016 in their statistical report.

This number remains to be significant as numerous individuals are stripped of their right to security. These stated facts and numbers prove the importance of the creation of Kalasag in the current society.

Theoretical Framework

One of the key concepts involved in the development of Kalasag is the process of design that will be used for creating it. Its core process is its idea of being human-centric based.

The Interaction Design Process Foundation's (2015) design thinking process explains that creating Human Centered design is the concept of creating solutions to problems that are feasible, viable, and desirable.

The Interaction Design Process Foundation has defined that creating human-centric designs follow a five-step process. These steps are used to ensure that designers are guided through the design process wherein it is centered on the needs of the target users.

The following are steps stated in the design process:

- A. Empathize: The step will be evaluating the user group through user-centric research. This will involve gathering second-hand resources about the condition of the user group. The step will also

include useability testing and content testing to identify user group experience.

- B. Define: From the raw data, I will organize data and make assumptions. Assumptions about the user group will be made through a journey map.
- C. Ideate: The user will use the current data at hand to propose different solutions to the defined problem. This involves applying free thinking.
- D. Prototype: This stage involves attempting to implement the project on a smaller scale. Different prototypes will be created based on ideas created in the ideation phase.
- E. Test: Prototypes created during the prototype phase will be tested on the user group. From this, an evaluation will be conducted on the feedback of the user group. Feedback will be documented to further improve the product before its implementation.

The Interaction Design Process Foundation also notes that the human-centric design process is iterative and cyclical. The steps mentioned above are not necessarily linear and can be revisited as new insights are gained throughout the process. The key focus of the process remains on understanding and prioritizing the needs of the users and involving them in the design decision-making process.

This theory of design played an essential role in this creative project as it emphasizes the role of the user group and addresses its needs in creating the project. With Kalasag being an original design and a creative project on the security of the PWD, this framework will ensure that the project provides a solution to the pending problem of the security of the PWD.

Conceptual Framework

This creative project created a Conceptual Framework through the iteration of the **Interaction Design Process Foundation on the subject of Human Centric design.**

The following diagram shows the relevance of user-centric design in the development of Kalasag. This diagram makes use of The Interaction Design Foundation's design process and the development design process as the highlight of the project toward the development of Kalasag.

In this conceptual model, I adapted the use of the Interaction Design Process Foundation on the subject of Human Centric design through their creative project to develop a wearable security jacket for the PWD. This project report is mainly dependent on human research and primary resources to create a jacket that influenced the final project, which is Kalasag: A Modern Security Jacket for Persons with Disabilities.

III. METHODOLOGY

Pre-Production Research

The following section discusses the steps that I took towards the development of Kalasag: A modern security jacket for Persons with Disability ages 18 above.

The pre-production research adopted a qualitative type of research which according to Bhandari (2023), is defined as an approach to the collection of non-numerical data to explain a certain phenomenon or topic. Specifically, I used the ethnographic research approach with autoethnography.

This project utilized a qualitative approach to elaborate on the methodology on how Kalasag was developed. This was also used to narrate personal encounters and insights on what I have learned and gathered about the target group through research and interaction. This particular methodology was used to emphasize the project's attributes and efficacy based on expert feedback.

To further discuss the project, the research design of the project revolved around an ethnographic approach to research. According to Caulfield (2022), an ethnographic approach to research is a method used to account for the experiences of the researcher. This method is used most especially when the researcher is studying the culture and behavior of a particular group of individuals.

In this capstone project, I used autoethnography to gather data on the development process of Kalasag. Autoethnography, as described by Hill (2017), involves analyzing and interpreting the researcher's personal experiences and observations. This autoethnographic approach was utilized in this creative project to document my insights based on personal experiences and perspectives. It allowed a better account of my immersion, active participation, and self-reflection towards the PWD community while acknowledging the subjective nature of knowledge production.

The research design employed in this capstone project serves to explicate how wearables can promote the security of the PWD and to articulate the developed design process experience behind the jacket.

Respondents Of The Study

The pre-production research included the participation of two key groups. The first group consisting of three key informants refers to those who participated in the pre-design stage of the project, which include: **clothing technology specialists (2)**, **deaf individual (1)**, and an **electronic engineer(1)**

Clothing technologist specialists refer to individuals who have studied clothing technology, are involved in the clothing industry, or are faculties in the college of clothing technology. They provided nsights into the marketability and effectiveness of the product.

An Electronic Engineer may be an individual who has a background in electronics, programming, and electronic safety precautions. This individual

evaluated whether the circuitry or programming of the device is correct and safe for stakeholders.

A Deaf individual may refer to any individual who is recognized by the government as a PWD and a person who has a long-term condition that does not allow the individual to hear or speak verbally. As this project was targeted to PWDs, an individual from the target group of stakeholders represented the sample group.

Following the pre-design data collection process, the next group of key informants refer to the sampled target group. This includes (3) deaf individuals who were tasked to give feedback regarding the final output of the project. This was done to validate the effectiveness of the product to the direct stakeholders.

Research Tools

A. Interview

The data-gathering process that was used was a semi-structured interview between its key informants. Doyle's (2022) online article states that a semi-structured interview is a data collection method that uses a prepared questionnaire to start the discussion while using open-ended questions to gather additional information. During the interview, I may ask additional follow-up questions that they deem useful to their research. This interview guaranteed that I was able to receive in-depth details on how to improve the product. The flexibility allowed key informants to also provide more information than expected.

This research tool was used for two of the phases of the project development: pre-design interview and post-production interview.

The pre-design interview guide aimed to gather data towards the foundation of the project. This includes finding the possible problem that the jacket may tackle and how this problem can be solved through expert insights. This is composed of two parts: topic-specific and user group specific. The first part focused on gathering data about the current issue of PWD while the second part tackled the behavior and preferences of the user group. Data from this interview guide was used as the building blocks of the design that was developed.

The post design interview guide is composed of three parts: 1.) Personal Preference 2.) Security Features 3.) Feedback and Recommendation. This final interview guide was used to draw conclusions on the effectiveness of the project as well as propose recommendations for future research about the topic. As the stakeholders and participants, this final interview was used to gather detailed feedback and recommendation towards improving the product.

With regards to the deaf, all interviews with the deaf were conducted online through written communication. Through the use of Google Forms, I supplied the user group with audiovisual materials that allowed the user group to evaluate the product in-depth. During the interview, the respondents were

also encouraged to ask open-ended questions in connection to possible opportunities and threats for the development of Kalasag.

B. Prototype

Part of this creative project was the development of a physical prototype of the jacket. After I determined the focus problem and the features that will address the problem, I accumulated the research into the creation of the jacket..

Through this creative project, an original, crafted jacket design was created. Once the development of the product is done, I presented this prototype to key informants. At the end of the creative project, this prototype was also submitted along with the written paper.

Data Gathering Procedure

The following was the data gathering process that I utilized throughout the design process of the project..

Phase 1: Empathize

This step included the evaluation of the user group through user-centric research. This involved gathering second-hand resources about the problems surrounding the user group. Before the development and designing of the project, I was able to gather data about the user group through key informant interviews or key research.

To gather these correspondents, a nonprobability sampling strategy was used. This creative project made use of the purposive sampling method. This term is used to refer to different techniques that are used to choose participants that fall under specific characteristics.

Specifically, I used an expert sampling method, which chooses participants based on their knowledge and expertise in a specific field that is being studied. This sampling method is found to be best for projects that are exploring a new topic without prominent researchers in the field.

During this process, I targeted to conduct an initial interview with the said key informants based on an interview guide. This phase aims to understand the user group and the current problem that should be addressed.

Phase 2: Define

From the raw data collected from the empathize stage, I organized the data and made several assumptions on the problem experienced by the user group. Upon defining the problems or the current situation of the user group, or the Deaf, the user then polished the defining phase by targeting one problem that they believe they can address and can be solved through current resources.

Phase 3: Design

From the current data at hand, I was able to propose a solution to the target group's problem. This involved applying free thinking and experimentation.

During this time, I generate solutions and ideas in relation to data that was gathered from the key informants. This process included sketching the prototype and plotting its possible features.

Phase 4: Prototype

This stage involves attempting to implement the project on a smaller scale. This involved creating the physical prototypes of the jacket with resources on hand.

I gathered the materials needed for the jacket based on the design drafted. The process began with creating the base jacket followed by the technological aspect attached to the clothing. Specifically, the technological aspect that was included was the use of Python Programming language and basic electronics. Once done, the jacket was initially tested by me for safety precautions.

Phase 5: Testing

During this stage, the output created in the prototype phase was presented to the user group. From this, an evaluation was conducted to gather feedback on the product. Feedback was documented to further improve the product and for the user to provide recommendations.

During this phase, I contacted key informants and discussed the functionality and stability of the product. Each key informant/participant was asked to evaluate the product. They went through a short semi-structured interview based on the questions that have been provided.

A letter and a consent form was created for the informant to sign before the interview that states that they consent to the interview. This letter included the affiliated university, my name, and the project that the person will partake in. This letter was signed by the PWD key informant to ensure the ethical measures.

Once the data gathering for the testing was done, I collated all the answers of the interviewees, noting common answers among the respondents as well as user-specific answers. These common answers were then documented as general recommendations for future studies. Additionally, answers that were in contrast to each other were documented as experimental recommendations that may be further explored in future studies towards expansion of the product.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following is an account of the design process of Kalasag from my perspective throughout all phases of the project.

Phase 1: Emphasize

One of the initial preparations I conducted for the design of the jacket was understanding the point of view of the target group through attending a basic awareness seminar for the deaf.

During the said event, the speaker highlighted that the current issue of the Deaf community concerns communication between the hearing and non-hearing. Due to the lack of interpreters in the country, it became more difficult for the deaf to be inclusive in all communities. This was the biggest challenge for the project's development— being able to create a jacket that will aid communication in emergency situations where a translator is not always provided.

Upon thorough review of resources, I identified common crimes associated with the PWD. Some of the most common ones include thievery and harassment.

Following initial research and preparation, I utilized free thinking to visualize the jacket and the possible output. The image below shows the sketch created.

Image 1: Initial Sketch of Kalasag

This sketch was also additionally presented to the key informants towards also polishing the possible idea.

The following is a summary of the results obtained from the Pre-design questionnaire from different specialists in the discipline:

a. Clothing Technology Experts

According to the two interviewed clothing technology experts, the design of the jacket must first and foremost be cotton based fabric such as sturdy twill or heavy twill. This is to ensure the safety of the wearer against electronic static and quality fabric. With the jacket promoting functionality, it was proposed that the jacket would have a plain design that has subdued color. Velcro was also proposed as the jacket’s closure type for better efficiency.

With the jacket as a multipurpose jacket, there is also a need to consider the cleaning process of the jacket. It was also suggested that the electronic components, such as the battery, can be inserted in the jacket through a detachable belt or through the use of a sheared compartment in the jacket. A safe compartment for the electronic components was also recommended.

Also, since the jacket is also catered to those individuals who commute, the experts emphasize the need for the jacket to possess additional functional features that will serve useful in cases of emergencies. Multifunctional pockets inside and outside the jacket were suggested for functionality. In terms of aesthetics, it is to be noted that the color of the jacket can be to the person's personal preference in terms of color and design.

Overall, the jacket was said to be a promising output but may pose feasibility issues in terms of the mass production of the jacket for future marketing purposes.

b. Electronics Engineer

For the electronic components of the jacket, the interviewed Electronic Engineer suggests the altering of the jacket for better incorporation of the electronics. While the original design of the jacket was unable to state where the electronics should be placed, the engineer proposed to place it in the underlining of the jacket.

In the case of the GPS tracker and Impact Sensor, the expert suggests the use of a small power supply that will help power the following features. On the contrary, the expert also concerns themselves with the use of the GPS tracking that will be against the data privacy of the wearer and whether this would be necessary to include such in the jacket.

Furthermore, the engineer emphasizes to consult future references regarding the creation of a security jacket in the Philippines as reference for the project.

c. User Group testing

Upon a written interview with a member of the deaf community, the individual's biggest concerns would be communication amongst authorities. The interviewed member states that the jacket must, more or so, help the individual seek for help. While deaf individuals have the capacity to maintain safety and independence, it is essential that the deaf may be able to seek assistance on their own through the english language or the use of Filipino Sign Language (FSL)

Additionally, the target user also emphasizes the need to be recognized as a deaf member in the community whilst outside so that they may be identified immediately.

Phase 2: Define

From the initial research results and experience, I became fixated on being able to create a means of communication for the Deaf community to achieve an immediate help response. In addition to this, I took note of the need to not only provide aid during security emergencies but also in calamity energies. This became the foundation of the jacket towards polishing the design.

Phase 3: Design

Upon the completion of the data gathering process from key informants, I reassessed the sketch that they initially created and began polishing the design, further improving certain features and removing unnecessary features that do not relate to the goal of the defined problem,

Image 2: Final draft of Kalasag

Generally, the concept that was developed for the jacket was that Kalasag would be a modern security jacket that promoted heightened security outdoors, including calamity emergencies for the PWD.

It aims to heighten individuals' security against common crimes and provide safety measures. Specifically, the jacket provides security features that allow PWD who are Deaf-classified individuals to be safe, especially during night or commute where danger usually occurs.

Its name roots from the Bisayan term "Kalasag " which means 'shield'. The jacket is meant to create an accessible, outdoor security measure for the PWD through merging the use of Information Communication Technology, electronics, and clothing technology.

In addition to its namesake, this jacket aimed to embody the tagline "Defending Diversity, Ensuring Security" wherein every feature of the jacket aims to protect the wellbeing of individuals.

The following are the final list of features of the jacket that resulted from the ideation phase:

A. Base Jacket

With the idea of the jacket being an outdoor wear with electronics, I aimed to create a simple jacket design, inspired by the silhouette and simplicity of the Mackintosh Jacket (British Fashion Council, n.d;).

The jacket aims to be practical, washable, and easy to use. The functionality of the jacket is also further emphasized with a secure pocket designed to carry supplementary security measures or necessary medication, affixed with a zipper closure for theft prevention.

Image 3: Sample of Mackintosh Jacket (Michael Andrews, n.d)

Its base jacket was made from denim, a cotton-based fabric that is known for its strong quality (Harris, n.d) . The fabric is also known for being an insulator, making it a nonconductor of electricity. This fabric is used to ensure that the garment is wearable and safe.

Furthermore, with regards to electronic circuits, the jacket includes a hidden compartment under the lining and the main fabric. This compartment assures the wearer that none of the electronic components will hurt them in any way.

In addition, the jacket also included neon stripes to provide enhanced visibility, particularly in dimly lit environments, ensuring the safety of the wearer in various contexts. Overall, this multifunctional security jacket demonstrates a comprehensive approach to safeguarding PWDs and addressing their unique needs.

B. Health Record

The jacket includes a QR Health record attached as a tag to the collar that serves as an identification item, in case of emergencies such as sudden faint or other need of medication, a witness present in the scene may offer help based on the person's current state.

Upon the scanning of the QR Code, the person who scanned the QR code will be directed to a simple application that will include important health information about the wearer of the jacket.

The said health record does not only include basic information and other medication, but also go in-depth in the disability information of the wearer by providing essential information on the disability that will help assist the person.

With health records being a confidential source of information, this app would also include a security log-in system for guests.

C. Security Alarm

To heighten the security of the jacket, specifically during theft, one of the garments features is to provide a preventive measure through a motion detector alarm. This activates once an intruder attempts to tug on the jacket forcefully. Through a pressure upon impact feature, the controller outputs a sounding alarm that notifies surrounding people of the wearer's emergency.

D. Help Caller

As the main feature of this jacket, a help caller was developed. This function was inspired by the data gathered through the target user group wherein the key informant pointed out the importance of being able to locate help centers independently.

The device would allow the wearer to send a distress signal to the nearest help center which will signal that a person is in need of assistance. Through this, the help center can answer the help call and immediately proceed to locating the person through their device.

Both parties will immediately meet halfway to address the user's concern faster. This will also allow Deaf individuals to immediately ask for help without the need of an ASL or FSL translator and during a case of thievery where no phone communication is present.

Phase 4: Prototype

The following is an account of how the prototype was built and how the features were developed individually:

A. Base Jacket

To achieve the jacket's desired design, I first searched for the targeted fabrics for the jacket. Upon thorough search through a fabric store, I ended up choosing a cotton and denim fabric with a deep blue color. Along with the fabric, I also bought other accessories that will be used for the jacket such as the zipper for the jacket's closure and a ribbon for the reflective stripes.

After this, I took the measurements of a mannequin. These measurements were then used to create the pattern of the jacket, customized to the mannequin's size.

Image 4 : In Progress Kalasag Jacket

Once the pattern was created, the pattern was then pinned on the fabric. The pieces were then cut and sewn together to make the base of the jacket. From this, the bodice of the jacket was assembled.

In addition to the bodice of the jacket, additional patterns were also cut, following the creation of the functional pockets of the jacket. These measurements from the jacket were taken from the bodice of the jacket and plotted into fabric. The pieces were then sown together to form the pockets.

Image 5: Pockets of Kalasag

Once the pockets were attached to the jacket, I proceeded to attach supplementary items such as the zipper that will serve as the jacket's closure and the neon stripes that will help visibility during the night.

Image 6: Neon Stripes and Zipper Closure of Kalasag

After the construction of the jacket, I then moved towards developing the electronics and digital elements involved in the jacket. However, this electronic compartment was developed later after the creation of the Security Alarm and Help Caller.

B. Health Record

The first security feature attached to the jacket was the QR health record that will serve as an identification item, in case of emergencies.

This Health Record was created through the use of Figma, a web application for interface design, to demonstrate a simple software that will let the Jacket user edit their record, but let outsider users merely view it.

Image 7: General Interface of Health Record

Ideally, the user or wearer of the jacket will first register to the app, where they will be able to input their basic information and essential health records. This part will include three main parts: 1.) Account Information which will include details that will identify the person in the app 2.) PWD Verification which will ensure that the person is legally considered as PWD and; 3.) Emergency Contact information which includes record of the emergency contact person in case of emergency.

Image 8: Sign Up process of Kalasag

Upon registration, the user will be able to input or edit their information to ensure that the record is updated in a timely manner.

With health records being a sensitive piece of information, the app also included a security measure during its development. Before the person who scans the QR Health Record code can access the record, they will be asked to input their information. Additionally, the app will also take a picture of the one

accessing the record for transparency for the wearer. As merely only a prototype, this application will not be implemented but will simulate the security of the app.

Image 9: Security Login Feature of Health Record

After the development of the simple software prototype, the link to this Figma prototype was then converted into a QR code through the use of a QR code generator. This was then printed on a sticker paper for fabrics and attached to the collar of the jacket.

Image 10: QR Health Record of Kalasag

C. Security Alarm

To achieve the security alarm, I made use of a micro:bit controller, which is an electronic component that will serve as the main controller of the jacket.

To create the alarm, I first identified the possible input and output feedback mechanism of the device. In this case, I made use of the Microbit controller's accelerometer to trigger the alarm. Specifically, when the controller detects an input strength of 120, the alarm then will be activated. In this way, the controller would output a sounding alarm that would notify surrounding people of the wearer's emergency.

This security alarm was made through the help of the Microsoft MakeCode editor which is an open source platform used to simulate real-life programming through the use of blocks of code.

Image 11 : Makerbit code used to program the Security Alarm

The image below shows how the security alarm was made through the use of the Makerbit Code. As seen, we can see how the code of this feature is merely a part of a bigger project, which is the help caller.

D. Help Caller

In making the Help caller, there were two things that the researcher had to consider: the physical placement of the device onto the jacket and the programming of the device.

For the programming of the Help Caller, I made use of the Microbit Controller’s radio feature, which allowed two devices to communicate with each other through signals. This ensures the two-way communication between the wearer of the jacket and the Help center through a specific dedicated device.

Similar to the Help Caller, the alarm was created through the use of the Microsoft MakeCode editor. Through a back and forth receiving and sending of radio signals, I was able to develop a device that will allow both the help center and jacket wearer to meet halfway during an emergency.

The usage of the jacket's Help Caller begins with a call for help. In the case that the user needs help, the user only needs to touch the logo of the device. Once the logo is touched, the user may select what type of help they need, may it be medical help or security help. Once they select the help they need, the controller will look for a help center that is able to receive the certain type of help signal.

Once the jacket controller finds an available help center, it will continue to receive its signal and display a proximity map that will help them locate the help center. This is simulated through the visual signal of the jacket wherein the controller's LED lights brighten upon nearing the other controller.

Simultaneously, the controller in the Help Center will release an auditory alarm that will note the center that someone is in need of help. Once they touch the logo of their controller, the help center will connect with the jacket controller and will immediately display a proximity map, similar to the one displayed by the jacket controller. Once the two controllers meet, both individuals can then press the controller to signal that they have completed the assist.

With the code already functional, I also proceeded to make the device itself through the combination of electronic parts.

Image 13 : Circuit Diagram of Kalasag

As seen above, I made use of the following diagram to create the device. Apart from the MicroBit controller, it can be seen that an LED screen was also attached to the controller for a better text display and two power sources to power up both the Microbit controller and the LED screen.

Having the diagram in mind, I then attached numerous pockets in the inner lining of the jacket. This then served as the electronic compartment of the jacket to avoid interference with the wearer's activities.

Image 14: Front and back view of the Help Caller

Phase 5: Testing

During the Post design process, I was able to gather insight into the project through an semi-structured interview with two deaf individuals from the institute. The following is a summary of the online interview conducted:

A. Personal Preference

According to the interviewees, the jacket's material is satisfactory to them as it resembles cotton or silk. However, it is noted that the jacket must be able to be customized based on the user's preference according to size and material used. One of the individuals mentioned that they would prefer the use of something more soft and smooth in comparison to denim while another mentioned that the jacket be fit to their frame and available in XXL sizes.

In terms of outdoor preference, the jacket is deemed effective. One of the notable features that was mentioned is the use of reflective stripes. Additionally, it is also noted that while the jacket may be effective outdoors, it is suggested to make the jacket more plain in design.

B. Security Features

1. QR Code Health Record

According to the interviewees, the QR Code Health record is indeed not a common feature that is seen in other devices. However, it may be deemed to be useful in certain situations.

2. Security Alarm

One of the current concerns of the interviewees is that the alarm may not allow the wearer to move safely perhaps due to the possible trigger mechanism of the alarm. It is recommended that the alarm would rather be triggered by the person itself in comparison to being activated through automatic means such as an accelerometer. Compared to the Health record, an interviewee deems this much more useful as a security feature.

3. Help Caller

Out of the three features, the Help Caller is the security feature that is deemed to be most useful out of the features. According to the user group, the key caller addresses communication, which is one of the current struggles of the Deaf Community today.

On the contrary, it should also be noted that this help caller might not always be useful, especially if there is a phone. One of the interviewees suggests that the effectiveness of the alarm will heighten when the help centers notice the help signal immediately and respond promptly to the help signal.

Over-all, the jacket indeed aids the Deaf in terms of security as it allows effective and clear communication, especially during an emergency situation. However, one of its current disadvantages is that the effectiveness of the device relies on the use of the English language. Not only should the device be written in the English language, but also the one handling the Help Center device. The sample target group points out that while the Deaf are more conversed in English, it is important that the one assisting should also be versed in the language in order for them to communicate further their situation amidst the jacket's assistance.

Collective Feedback

According to the respondents, the main stockholders of this jacket would mostly be individuals from the age of 7-12 years old, or individuals who are considered to be young adults or minors.

For further improvement of the jacket, one of the most common answers among the respondents is the use of vibration as an output signal for the device, in addition to the light mechanism as this would be more sensitive and felt by non-hearing individuals.

Overall, the jacket is favored by the current target group due to its key objective of being able to aid in communication between the hearing and non-hearing during emergency situations.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

SUMMARY

It is indeed worth noting that the needs of our Persons with Disability in the country have yet to be attained, as the country continues to face numerous, countless incidents of crimes against Persons with Disabilities. While the local government has enforced laws aiding benefits to the community, their security is indeed a right that must be protected with the help of modern technology.

Amidst the digital age, humans are able to make use of existing technologies towards developing new solutions to humanitarian problems. One of the existing technologies is the development of wearables in the Philippines that have continuously grown in the last century. While the use of wearables are now being used in the field of medical care, it is time that we explored its use for security for the minority that is Persons with Disability.

With this in mind, I developed this project known as Kalasag, a modern security jacket for the PWD with a specific target group for the Deaf Community. The aim of this project is to discover how wearables may aid in the security of persons with disability and accounting the design process behind its creation.

Embodying the framework of human centric designing, the project aims to replicate its five-step process ie. Empathize, Define Ideate, Prototype, Test.

The project first began with a pre-design written interview where I collected professional opinion from respective professionals and one from the target group. Through this, I focused on the target group's problem of unable to seek help when needed. This became the main pain point and focus of the said thesis through a functional jacket with four important functions, including the following: QR Code as Health Record, Help Caller, Security Alarm, and functional jacket.

The assembly of the jacket began with cresting the jacket itself, inspired from the Mchintosh jacket, praised by its functional and practical silhouette. This base jacket was then customized through the addition of electronics.

At the end of the design process, I concluded this project with a focus group discussion with selected individuals involved with the Deaf community to develop the project further and gain additional insight to the project's flaws and effectiveness.

Conclusion

As the end of the project comes to a close, it is with utmost importance to highlight the need for a means of security among PWD members with an exploratory with the use of wearables to further promote communication of the Deaf community with the hearing community towards inclusivity as members of society as the number of crime cases against these individuals continue to rise.

Through the development of this project, gathered data shows that while the Deaf community remains to be perceived as independent, communication still continues to be an unceasing problem due to the lack of hearing individuals in the community who know how to communicate through Filipino Sign Language.

Amongst the security features present, one of the most notable and positively perceived is the Help Caller which allowed an individual to contact for help with the absence of the phone. According to the target group, the product promoted efficient and immediate help response to those in need.

On the contrary, one of the problems that this jacket encountered is its personal preference amongst individuals. Numerous features, such as the jacket's material and style, as well as the security alarm, can still be improved in such a way that the jacket will allow the wearer to customize it to their preferences.

Nevertheless, the jacket overall shows positive feedback on its potential as a security jacket for the Deaf.

Recommendation

This creative project shows potential on how wearables can be further developed to create solutions to the security of individuals, hearing or non hearing. In the case of the development of Kalasag, there is much need to

further develop this project through the incorporation of high end technology and upscaled projects.

General Recommendation

This creative project focused on the development of the jacket functions on basic programming and limited capabilities. Due to the small scale prototype, numerous functions have yet to be improved towards streamlining safety and precautions.

To enhance the jacket's safety features, it is crucial to refine the Help Caller system to ensure it is both effective and responsive. This involves improving the reliability of the system by guaranteeing swift response times from help centers and exploring the possibility of integrating it with existing communication devices, if necessary, to provide a seamless and immediate means of assistance.

Additionally, the security alarm mechanism should be revised to allow manual activation by the wearer, rather than relying on automatic triggers. This adjustment would address concerns related to movement safety and grant users greater control over when the alarm is activated. Moreover, incorporating a vibration mechanism in addition to or as an alternative to audible alarms could significantly enhance its effectiveness for Deaf individuals, ensuring that the alarm is perceived through tactile feedback as well as sound.

Additionally, with the Health record implemented merely through Figma, it would be better developed if the Health record software incorporates the use of the internet to provide real time information that can be edited by the user.

Experimental Recommendation

In addition to recommendations on how to improve the jacket's security features, it is also recommended that future prayers of this project may experiment on catering for the wearer's preferences.

To better cater to diverse personal preferences and body types, it is essential to offer a range of material and size options for the jacket. This could include soft fabrics such as cotton or silk and accommodating a broad spectrum of sizes, including XXL. Implementing a modular design would allow users to select the fabric and size that best suit their needs, enhancing both comfort and fit.

Additionally, in response to feedback favoring a more understated design, simplifying the jacket's appearance while retaining its essential reflective safety features may be experimented. This approach would make the jacket more versatile, ensuring it is not only functional in emergency situations but also suitable for everyday wear, thus broadening its appeal and usability.

Furthermore, with the jacket developed with the target group of Deaf individuals, it is recommended to conduct further studies on how wearables

can continue to aid different types of Persons with Disabilities, especially those with mental impairment that have been the top victims of crime with the PWDs.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A: Request Letter for Interview

January 26, 2023

PERSONS WITH DISABILITY AFFAIRS OFFICE

Ground floor Community Center Building,

Quezon City Hall Compound,

Quezon City, Philippines

To whom may it concern,

I am Hannah D. Beraquit, a fourth-year student in the Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia Studies (BAMS) program at the University of the Philippines, Open University. In accordance with our Capstone Project course requirement, I am writing to possibly request a key informant from the PDAO to contribute to the creative project.

My research titled "Kalasag: A modern security jacket for PWD" aims to create a wearable technological device that promotes the independence of the PWD against crimes such as theft and sexual harassment by utilizing modern technology. This creative project intends to develop a prototype of a wearable jacket that will help enhance the safety and well-being of individuals of the Deaf community.

For this creative project, I am hoping to connect with a Deaf individual or professional who can represent the Deaf community to provide feedback or data regarding this project and the security of Deaf individuals through a

30-minute interview. Rest assured, the interview with the selected key informant will be scheduled based on their availability.

Please see the following document for project details and plan for the interview. For inquiries, you may contact me through my mobile number 09452967752 or email me at hdberaquit@up.edu.ph.

Thank you for taking the time to consider my request. I am hopeful for a positive response.

Gratefully yours,

Hannah Beraquit

Student No: 2019-05566

UPOU - BA in Multimedia Studies

APPENDIX B: Pre-design Interview Guide Questionnaire (Expert Interview)

Key Informant Profile

Respondent number :

Date of Interview:

Name of Faculty :

Age:

Gender: Male, Female

Degree:

Years of Work Experience in the industry:

Duration of the interview:

Type of interview:

Location:

University of the Philippines Diliman, C.P Garcia

Contact number:

Email Address:

Instructions:

Step 1: The research student will present the initial design to the key informant interview

Step 2: The research student will gather information and feedback using the interview guide.

Description: This interview will be 15 minutes long depending on your answer and will have three parts. (1) Design Components (2) Concept Design (3) Recommendation

Questions:

Part 1. Design Components

1. What are your initial thoughts about the concept of the initial design?

Suggestion

- a. Fabric:
- b. Pattern:
- c. Texture:
- d. Color:
- e. Materials: (What type of closure would be more efficient to use eg. zippers, velcro?)

Part 2. Concept Design

1. Do you have experience in designing clothing for PWD? If yes
 - 1.1 What are the challenges of designing clothes for PWD disability?
 - 1.2 If no. What do you think are the challenges of designing clothes for PWD disability?
2. What consideration would you recommend in designing clothes for PWD?
3. What technological features?
 - 3.1 Other than the ones mentioned in the design, are there other functionalities that you think would come in handy?
4. How much is considered a budget friendly security jacket? Estimate (Price range)
5. Can you suggest which part of the jacket can add the technological components such as batteries ?

Part 3: Recommendations

What is your overall feedback on the project ?

APPENDIX C: Pre-design Interview Guide Questionnaire (User Group Interview)

Key Informant Profile

Respondent number :

Date of Interview:

Name of Faculty :

Age:

Gender:

Degree:

Years of Work Experience in the industry:

Type of interview:

Duration of the interview:

Location:

Contact number:

Email Address:

Instructions:

Step 1: The research student will present the initial design to the key informant interview

Step 2: The research student will gather information and feedback using the interview guide.

Description: This interview will be 30 -60 minutes long depending on your answer and will have three parts. (1) Design Components (2) Concept Design (3) Recommendation

Questions:

Part 1. Design Components

1. What are your initial thoughts about the concept of the initial design?
 - a. Technological GPS tracking
 - b. Impact Sensor
 - i. Power source
 - ii. Microcontroller
 - iii. Circuit diagram
 - iv. Software for coding
 - c. Suggestion GPS tracking
 - i. Power source
 - ii. Microcontroller
 - iii. Circuit diagram
 - iv. Software for coding
 - v. (What type of closure would be more efficient to use eg. zippers, velcro?)

Part 2. Concept Design (Workshop)

Instruction:

Design Sketching

We are going to have a sketch exercise: Can you help me create a possible diagram on which part of the jacket can add the technological components such as batteries ?

How can we seamlessly integrate electronic components to the wearable technology

1. Placement of powersource
2. Electronic pathway of electronic components

Recommendations: What is your overall feedback on the project ?

APPENDIX D: Post-Design Questionnaire (User Group Interview)

Key Informant Profile

Respondent number :

Date of Interview:

Age:

Gender: Male, Female

Type of interview: Face to Face or Remote

Duration of the interview:

Location:

Contact number:

Email Address:

Instructions:

Step 1: The research student will present the initial design to the key informant.

Step 2: The research student will gather information and feedback using the interview guide.

Description: This interview will be 15 minutes long depending on your answer and will have three parts. (1) Design Components (2) Concept Design (3) Recommendation

Questions:

1. Design Components

- What challenges or concerns do you face in security situations that a specialized jacket could address?
- What should be considered to ensure ease of movement and comfort for you?
- Are there any materials or textures that you find particularly comfortable or uncomfortable to wear?
- Are there any color preferences or visibility considerations that would be important for the jacket?
- Are there any medical considerations or sensitivities that should be taken into account during the design process?
- Would you prefer a jacket that is more discreet or one that clearly identifies you as someone who may need assistance?
- What types of closures or fasteners would be easiest for you to manage eg. zipper, buttons, and such?

2. Concept Design

- What features or functionalities do you think would make a security jacket most helpful for your needs?
- Can you describe any specific scenarios where a security jacket would be beneficial for you?
- In what ways could the jacket assist in communication, especially if you have speech or hearing impairments?
- Are there any additional thoughts or ideas you have about the design or functionality of the jacket?

3. Recommendation

What is your overall feedback on the project ?

APPENDIX E: Post Design Questionnaire For Target Group

Key Informant Profile

Respondent number :

Date of Interview:

Name:

Age:

Gender: Male, Female

Duration of the interview:

Type of interview:

Location:

Contact number:

Email Address:

Instructions:

Step 1: The research student will present the project to the key informant interview

Step 2: The research student will gather information and feedback using the interview guide.

Description: This interview will be 15 minutes long depending on your answer and will have three parts. (1) Personal Preference (2) Features (3) Feedback and Recommendation

A. PERSONAL PREFERENCE

- How does the jacket feel in terms of comfort and fit?

- Does the jacket's design meet your style preferences?
- How do you resonate with the jacket's design as a PWD?
- Does the jacket's visibility (e.g., reflective strips) meet your needs when outdoors?

B. FEATURES

- How effective are the jacket's security features in making you feel safe?
 - Jacket
 - Health Record
 - Security Alarm
 - Help Caller
- How easy is it to operate the security features, such as alarms or alerts?
- Do you think the jacket aids communication between the deaf and speaking individuals?

C. FEEDBACK AND RECOMMENDATION

- Would you recommend this jacket to other deaf individuals for its security features?
- How does this jacket compare to other security products you have used?
- Are there any additional features you would like to see in a future version of the jacket?
- Overall, how would you rate the jacket's usefulness and effectiveness for your security needs?

APPENDIX F: Informed Consent Form for Research Informants

This informed consent form is for key informants and who we are inviting to participate for our Bachelor's Thesis, titled "***Kalasag: A modern security jacket for the PWD***"

Introduction

I am Hannah Beraquit, 4th Year student under the BA in Multimedia Studies program of the University of the Philippines, Open University. This creative project aims to create a wearable technological device that promotes the independence of the PWD against crimes such as theft and sexual harassment by utilizing modern technology. This creative project intends to develop a prototype of a wearable jacket that will help enhance the safety and well-being of Persons with Disability

Purpose of the Research

This research will involve your participation in a short-interview that will take about 30-45 minutes. You are being invited to take part in this research as a key informant that can contribute much to our understanding and knowledge of wearables and/or the PWD in the Philippines.

Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary. It is your choice whether to participate or not. If you accept, you will take part in this interview based on your convenience. The information recorded is confidential, and no one else except me will have access to the information documented during the interview process. The entire interview will be tape-recorded, but no-one will be identified by name on the tape.

There will be no direct benefit to you, but your participation is likely to help us find out more about the production of wearables and user data on the mute

PWD in the Philippines. You will not be provided with any incentive to take part in the research. However, we will give you a token of appreciation for your time or travel expenses.

The researcher will not be disclosing information about you to anyone outside of the research team and will anonymously document the results of the interview in the final research output. The raw data gathered from this will be deleted after one year after publishing the final paper. We will keep the information gathered from this capstone project private. It will not be distributed or shared with anyone. The knowledge that we get from this research will be shared with you and your community before it is made widely available to the public. The results will be summarized for each participant.

If you have any questions, you can ask them now or later. If you wish to ask questions later, you may contact the following:

Researcher: Hannah D. Beraquit

Address: 186 P.R. Sotto St. Brgy. Tibagan, San Juan City.

Phone Number: 09452967752

E-Mail: hdberaquit@gmail.com / hdberaquit@up.edu.ph

Certificate of Consent

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this creative project.

Printed Name of the Key informant _____

Signature of Participant _____

Date

Day/month/year

Statement by the Person Taking Consent

I confirm that the participant was given an opportunity to ask questions about the creative project, and all the questions asked by the participant have been answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

A copy of this ICF has been provided to the participant.

Printed Name of the Researcher Hannah Beraquit

Signature of the Researcher

Date

Day/month/year

APPENDIX G: Demonstration Video of Security Features

HELP CALLER VIDEO DEMO: https://youtu.be/qjR_LQ-DcEo

SECURITY ALARM VIDEO DEMO: <https://youtu.be/oHDJW45-1HY>

QR HEALTH CODE RECORD PROTOTYPE:

<https://www.figma.com/proto/DMIWcnvAC2F8DZMteMeRwn/Kalasag-Health-Record?node-id=0-1&t=NB9GWt4Mvdsq8eUx-0&scaling=scale-down&content-scaling=fixed&page-id=0%3A1&starting-point-node-id=2%3A8&show-proto-side-bar=1>

APPENDIX H: Microbit Controller Code

The image displays Microbit Controller Code for a Receiver, consisting of several interconnected blocks:

- on start:**
 - radio set group 1
 - radio set transmit power 1
 - connect I2C at I2C address 20
 - I2C102 show "Hannah Stewart" at position 1 with length 15
 - I2C102 show "Suzy" at position 17 with length 11
 - set accelare to true
 - set map to false
- on button A pressed:**
 - stop all sounds
- forever loop:**
 - if helpCaller == true then
 - set accelare to false
 - else
 - if acceleration (g) strength > 1700 then
 - repeat 3 times
 - play melody at tempo 200 (bpm) until done

- on logo pressed:**
- I2C102 show "Select Help Type" at position 1 with length 15
- I2C102 show "A.Pack 3.Security" at position 17 with length 15
- set helpCaller to true
- on button A+B pressed:**
- radio send needMeds
- on radio fndMeds received:**
- play melody at tempo 200 (bpm) until done
- I2C102 show "Found Red Help" at position 1 with length 15
- I2C102 show "Follow rules" at position 17 with length 15
- set map to true
- on radio methods received:**
- play melody at tempo 200 (bpm) until done
- I2C102 show "Pack is on the way" at position 1 with length 15
- repeat 100 times
 - radio send string
- pause (ms) 500
- on button A+B pressed:**
- set map to false
- clear screen
- I2C102 show "Assist Complete" at position 1 with length 15
- I2C102 show "Pin reset alarm time" at position 17 with length 15
- play melody at tempo 200 (bpm) until done
- stop all sounds
- set helpCaller to false
- pause (ms) 500
- on radio received receivedString:**
- if map == true then
 - set hlpSignal to received packet signal strength
 - plot bar graph of map hlpSignal from low -95 high -42 to low 0 high 9
 - up to 9
 - if hlpSignal >= -42 then
 - play melody at tempo 300 (bpm) in background
- on start (Receiver):**
- radio set group 1
- radio set transmit power 1
- set map to false
- forever (Receiver):**
- pause (ms) 1000
- radio send string "1"
- on radio needMeds received:**
- play melody at tempo 120 (bpm) looping in background
- show string "Help Needed"
- radio send fndMeds
- on logo pressed (Receiver):**
- stop all sounds
- play melody at tempo 500 (bpm) until done
- radio send asstMeds
- clear screen
- set map to true
- on button A+B pressed (Receiver):**
- clear screen
- set map to false
- play melody at tempo 200 (bpm) until done
- stop all sounds
- show string "Assist Completed"
- on radio received receivedString (Receiver):**
- if map == true then
 - set hlpSignal to received packet signal strength
 - plot bar graph of map hlpSignal from low -95 high -42 to low 0 high 9
 - up to 9
 - if hlpSignal >= -42 then
 - play melody at tempo 300 (bpm) in background

Microbit Controller Code for Receiver